

SEMANTICS OF INTRODUCTORY ELEMENTS IN A COMMUNICATIVE-PRAGMATIC ASPECT

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Abstract:

The article deals with the study of introductory elements are essential components of writing that serve to establish context, provide background information, and engage readers at the beginning of a piece of text. These elements help set the stage for what follows, capture the reader's attention, and guide them into the main body of the content.

Key words: concept, mercy, rumor, hypotheticality, imperative speech genres.

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The emotive-qualified talking subject characterizes and emotionally evaluates reality (fortunately, to great surprise, unfortunately, to amazement, to disappointment, etc.) serve to express the attachment of a given opinion or assessment to a particular subject sphere (according to rumors, in my opinion; I remember, it is known, according to opinion, by conviction, by reasoning, by concept (someone or someone), by reports (someone or someone), by view (someone, someone); from the Kcht '.iia point, etc.) implement "this contact" at all phases of speech communication: establishment, maintenance, opening of speech contact (you see (you), you know (you), you understand, understand, you understand, imagine, imagine, imagine, (by) listen (by) listen, hear, hear, do mercy, etc.) are implemented in situations where the speaker needs to focus on all or part of the utterance; the speaker purposefully insists on a certain nomination (undoubtedly, indeed, of course, of course, of course, etc.) by linking parts of the text (individual sentences, paragraphs) are a specific means of interfacial and interabase communication; help the speaker (writer) solve a number of pragmatic problems: to logic the text, giving it harmony, to arrange the course of his reasoning, etc., in this way, in addition, in the end, in general, on the one hand - on the other hand, for example, first of all, by the way, they demonstrate the fact of presumption, uncertainty, hypotheticality, express doubt about the truth of the statement (it seems that there probably should be, probably, a pin.)

Communication and pragmatic settings implemented by introductory elements

1. Show different degrees of Schtzenki on the good/bad axis.
 2. The affective states of the subject are expressed.
 3. The general charge of emotions already functioning in expression is strengthened.
 4. The categorical statement is veiled.
 5. Indicates uncertainty of the statement from the point
1. Increase the degree of reliability of the presented information in the eyes of the addressee by referring to another guarantor.
 2. Shifting the epistemic responsibility of the content of the statement to more competent sources.

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3. The effect of cooperation is realized when the addressee mentally cooperates his own opinion with the opinion of the competent source, mentally agreeing with him.

4. Reduce the degree of categorical utterance.

5. Encourage the addressee to accept the author's point of view.

1. Express emotional qualifications about the reported.

2. Being included in the situation of speech communication, they are able to characterize the non-event point of view of the communicant.

3. The trivial state of affairs is marked.

4. Exclude possible doubts of the interlocutor, that is, the information contained in the statement is presented as appellative.

5. They organize a specific form of the polemical relationship between the argument and the counterargument in the statement;

6. Reduce the categorical statement, optimizing further speech communication, leaving the interlocutor the right to his own opinion and the opportunity to be heard;

1. Focus the interlocutor's attention on all the statement or any part of it;

2. Give the message greater confidence;

3. A voluntary property used in imperative speech genres (request, persuasion, plea, demand);

4. Statements are able to prepare "favorable ground" for the upcoming message. Such a message contains either a vital inf for the interlocutor

5. Voicing the categorical nature of the statement;

6. Emotional state of communicator is objectified.

1. Strengthen the hypothetical statement.

2. Create an ironic tone of the statement.

3. Reduce the degree of categoricity of the statement;

4. Indirectly indicate authorization;

5. The introduction to the statement of accent-but-probabilistic introductory constructions allows the communicator to objectify such feelings as hope, fulfillment of desires;

6. Representing the course of reasoning of the communicator, they are able to express the consequence of the provisions specified in the text.

1. Focus the interlocutor's attention on a certain nomination in the text;

2. Indicate a greater or lesser degree of significance of a sign in the text;

3. Logize the text, while revealing the course of reasoning of the communicator;

4. Mark the trivial state of affairs;

5. Submit an author's comment in relation to a particular situation;

6. Emotional evaluation is marked

Text-propositional insertion elements are textual, explaining, clarifying the propositional content of statements in the text; complementing the dominant content of the text; commenting on the choice of certain speech means. SCH Classification of insert elements in the communicative-pragmatic aspect

Emotive evaluation inserts

The inset elements of the contamination type are most "tied" to the personality of the speaker, indicating his social and personal status; clearly expressing the emotive-but-evaluative attitude of the speaker: to the content of the text, to the genre of the text and to the addressee. combine the communicative-pragmatic load of text-positive and emotive-evaluative insert elements. clarifies the information of the main content of the statement by indicating a possible alternative situation;

Transmits information as reliable or problematic; focuses the interlocutor's attention on the information presented in the content of the main statement; maximally adapts the transmission of information to the perception of the addressee; reduces categorical speech; increases the degree of reliability of information due to the cited source; represents the course of reasoning of the communicator. communicate, clarify or clarify the information necessary for an adequate perception of the thought conveyed by the main statement; strengthen the impression of the statement by giving a subjective assessment of the reported; comment on what is reported in the main statement in a more concise or, conversely, detailed form. enter positive, negative information in relation to the statement described in the main statement; in relation to yourself or the design of a speech; create an ironic tone of utterance; to vualize the categorical nature of the statement.

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